

Evaluation the skillful performance of Algerian soccer players during the cometition.

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to evaluate some of the characteristics of the defensive and offensive skill performance during the competition among professional soccer players in the Algerian professional league.

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the sheef observation was used by the researcher to evaluate the effectiveness of the performance of basic skills during the competition and to determine their participation in total skill performance.

The study sample consisted of (72) professionals' players, the results showed that the efficiency of the skill performance during the competition for Algerian professional players is weak and there is a difference between the representation of basic skills in skill performance with a great advantage for the basic offensive skills.

The study recommended the use of modern technologies to develop the skillful performance of athletes, and pay attention to the principle of individual training when teaching and mastering basic skills.

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1.Introduction:

Performance in ball games is much more difficult to appraise than it is in individual sports. In track-and-field athletics the competitor who passes the winning post first, jumps highest or longest, or throws the missile furthest becomes victorious. All competitors can be judged according to their finishing position, or on the time taken or distance achieved during performance. These kinds of metrics apply also to swimming, rowing, cycling, skiing and other events. In ball games the contest is decided by points or sets won, or goals scored. In soccer there is a simple determinant of victory: winning means scoring more goals than the opposition. (Carling, 2007)

Soccer is a complex sport activity, whose success depends on various variables and factors, including physiological abilities and technical. (Kellis & Katis, 2007)

Also soccer requires more individual and collective preparation, more comprehensive and accurate because of the increasing number of competition, the shrinking rest periods and the growing of the requirements of the professional practice of his sport. (Thomas R., 2007)

The computer video analysis systems have been gradually adopted by professionals from elite teams who seek to improve their understanding of the performance of their players and of course Improve their results during competitions. Performance analysis using video and computer is a way to study the characteristics of individual and collective sports, technical and tactical performance. The information provided by the analysis systems helps design and implement training programs based on player performance.

The coaching process can be thought of as an ongoing cycle of performance and practice. The role of the coach is to observe and analyse the performance and provide feedback, which can be incorporated into planned practice that should theoretically lead to enhanced performance. Successful coaching depends, among other things, on the accuracy of the observation and how well it is analysed. It is therefore extremely important that the information collected during athletic performance is objective, unbiased, accurate and as comprehensive as possible. (Hughes & Franks 2008).

These tools provide detailed statistical information on the strengths and weaknesses of the team and the opponents in that one helps to select and recruit the best players during matches. It also provides the ability to create a database to store and process all types of performance information

for any given time period. This enables the instructor to assess the evolution of his team's performance during the entire season.

In modern soccer, the skillful performance plays a major role in achieving positive results for the team, as it directly affects the process of mastery and success of the tactics and the system of the team. The ability to execute skilled movement patterns efficiently and effectively is the most important aspect of soccer performance and players must apply cognitive, perceptual and motor skills to rapidly changing situations. There have been attempts to measure these parameters for talent identification (or development) purposes and skill acquisition and intervention research. (Ali A., 2011)

Also the achieving of the tactical objectives during the soccer match depends on the proficiency of the players for all skills that are done using or without the ball, which is in the application of the method of play while respecting the competition law (Döbler, 1988).

Many researchers believe that skill performance is the basic rule of soccer during competition because skills are the important factor for professional soccer. Without a player's basic skills, he cannot carry out the plans or perform his duties properly, the mastery of basic skills requires long training, this training is considered the backbone of the daily training unit. (Eriksson and coll, 2001, Dellal and coll, 2008)

Skill performance is the essence of the player's performance during the competition in modern soccer is a reflection of the other aspects of sports performance because the master's in the basic skills such as passing, shooting, tackling and receiving the ball is only an indication of the development of physical abilities and psychological preparation for the interplay and interdependence of the components of sports performance and mutual influence. (Di Salvo and coll, 2007)

Hence the importance of studying and analyzing the technical performance of the players during the competition because it allows the measurement and evaluation of the performance of the players as well as the team both in competitions or in training. Many coaches record and analyze the performance of their players and teams to find the best ways to increase their effectiveness during the competitions, and the ability to see the data recorded by one of the important drivers that lead to correct errors and follow progress. (Mackenzie & Cushion, 2012)

The researcher conducted a survey of some of the professional soccer clubs in Algeria. We found that the coaches of these teams do not rely on the method of analyzing games to evaluate the performance of their

players during the competition, but through interviews with these trainers revealed to us that they evaluate the performance of their players during training only through The technical tests and they during the competition evaluate the performance of these players by relying on observation with the naked eye and memory. They do not recognize the importance of analytical techniques that allow to give a true picture of what actually happens in the stadium by assessing the actual performance of the players and tracking the status of the team and progress during the matches, which led the researcher to study some of the characteristics of the performance skills during the competition of professional soccer players, Using the forms of observation and audiovisual means, especially in the absence of Algerian scientific studies that has not been interested in studying this subject, and through our research we ask about the most important characteristics of the performance skill during the competition of professionals soccer players.

2.Method and Materials

2.1. method of observation:In our current study, we designed an observation sheet to measure and evaluate the skill level of soccer players during the competition. We took into consideration the basic skills most frequently used by high-level soccer players during defense and attack, and because the athletic performance of the athlete is reflected in the proficiency of the skills in the game and its completion effectively, after the study tool is presented for arbitration by specialized experts, we will use the efficiency factor to determine the skill level of the professional players during the competition.

The observation sheet used in our study allows us to measure the effectiveness of the performance of the most important defensive and offensive skills used by players during competition. These skills are:

-Receiving the ball; Shooting the ball; Dribbling; Passing; Tackling; Hit with the head; Running with the ball.

2.2. Materials:

Computer equipped with: The KMPlayer

□ Match videos.

(KMPlayer) is a program that works to read and play various types of video, this program contains many distinctive features including:

- Video speed control.
- Progress and re-video with (5) seconds.
- Convert video to 3D.
- Return to the previous file.

- Stop and play the section.
- Sound control.
- Make the program take the whole screen.

The following figure shows the program window (KM Player):

Figure (1): Window of the programme (KM Player)

2.3. Participants :

The study community consists of the total number of athletes practicing soccer in the professional clubs (16). According to the Algerian federal soccer laws, the team has the right to call (18) players to participate during matches during the sports season. Due to the lack of material and human resources available, the researcher selected a sample of (72) athletes. This sample is homogeneous. It is composed of athletes of the same sex (males), They practice the same sports discipline (soccer) and play the same level (the first professional league), The following table illustrates the characteristics of the study sample:

Table1: the characteristics of the study sample

Clubs	Number of individuals	Age (years)	Height (cm)	Weight (Kg)	Experience (years)
Union Biskra (Algeria)	18	27.90 ±3.53	177.81 ±7.33	72 ±5.07	8.81 ±3.15
Essa Staifi (Algeria)	18	26.76 ±4.04	180.23 ±6.45	76.61 ±6.86	7.46 ±3.40
Defense of the Taganant (Algeria)	18	26.64 ±3	179.2 ±5.31	72.64 ±5.41	7.71 ±2.91
The Sporting Club of Constantine (Algeria)	18	26.28 ±2.12	179.5 ±6.73	74.85 ±6.80	7.50 ±2.02

2.4. Design and Procedure :

In order to achieve the research objectives, the researcher carried out the following field procedures:

- Perform an observation sheet to observe and evaluate the skillful performance of soccer players during competition and present it to a group of experts for judging.
- Record the matches to be observed on CD-ROM.
- Conducting an analysis of the skill performance based on the observation sheet and audiovisual aids.
- Collect and analyze data obtained.
- Explain, interpret and discuss the results of the data obtained.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

We used the Excel Stat. program to calculate the various descriptive statistical indicators used in the study, which are:

- Repetition
- Arithmetic average
- standard deviation
- percentage
- Coefficient of effectiveness

3. Results

In this section of our study, we presented and analyzed the results obtained from observing the technical-tactical performance of some professional teams in the Algerian championship (C.S.Constantine., E.S.Staifi., U.S.Biskra, D.S.Tajnant.)

Firstly, we presented the results of the percentage of effectiveness of the defensive and offensive skills performance during the competition, secondly, we presented the results of the defensive and offensive performance during

the competition, thirdly, we presented the results of the percentage of participation of defensive and offensive skills in the overall technical-tactical performance during the competition, and finally, we presented the results of the percentage of defensive and offensive performance during the competition.

3.1. The effectiveness of the defensive and offensive skills performance during the competition

Figure (2) shows the radar of the effectiveness of the implementation of basic skills by professional athletes during the competition.

The above figure represents the maximum performance radar the athlete can perform during the competition (red space). The data recorded in the figure shows a contraction of the skill performance performed by athletes during the competition and its proximity to the radar center (green space) This is what enables us to say that the efficiency of the skillful performance during the competition performed by the professional athletes during the competition is weak and far from the perfect skill performance.

3.2. The effectiveness of defensive and offensive performance during the competition

Figure (3): The effectiveness of defensive and offensive skill during competition

During the competition, the skill performance is divided into two parts: the offensive skill performance and the defensive skill performance. Therefore, we will study the effectiveness of each of its during the competition. The data obtained in the previous figure show that the performance of the offensive skill is higher than the performance of the defense skill (39.69% vs. 26.97%), Which shows that the players' performance of the basic offensive skills during the competition, such as receiving, passing and shooting of the ball was more effective compared to the performance of basic defense skills such as the tackling and hit the ball with the head.

3.3. the percentage of participation of defensive and offensive skills

Figure (4): Percentage of each skill in technical performance during competition.

From the data shown in the previous figure, we conclude that there is a wide variation in the ratio of the representation (Taux de Fréquence) every skill in the technical performance of skills during the competition, that is, there are basic skills performed by the frequency of large players unlike other basic skills performed very reluctantly, where We find that the skills of receiving the ball and passing the ball are the two main skills most implemented during the competition by the players, they represent the highest percentage of (35.10%) and (35.28%), respectively. While the Tackling and the shooting are achieved very little during the competition, their percentage of technical performance was estimated at (2%) for each skill.

3.4. the percentage of defensive and offensive performance during the competition.

Figure(5): percentage of offensive and defensive skill performance during competition

Based on the data shown in the previous figure, we found that the performance percentage of the offensive skill is much higher than percentage of the defensive skill (72.03% vs. 27.97%), meaning that the players perform basic offensive skills during the competition at a greater frequency compared to their implementation of basic defense skills.

4. Discussion

In our study of the technical performance of professional soccer players, we found that the effectiveness of the implementation of basic skills was weak and in most of the basic skills studied (shooting, dribbling, running and hit with the head), except for the effectiveness of the skills of receiving the ball and passing the ball that has a medium level. Overall, the effectiveness of defensive and offensive performance by players was weak (26.97% and 39.69%), respectively.

The weakness of the efficiency of technical performance by professional players during the competition may be attributed to factors such as the small variety of training methods and the lack of reliance on individual training in attaining the basic skills and the development of physical characteristics, as well as the lack of means especially in the young players because they are very important in learning and mastering the various skills Basic activity.

The use of various exercises (2 m × 2 m), (3 m × 5 m) and gradient in the area up to (8 m × 8 m) using small spaces has a significant impact on the improvement and learning and mastering the basic skills in soccer. In this context (Rada and coll, 2019) indicates that playing in a small space makes the athlete proficient in playing skillfully. The results of the study of (Serranojmrs and coll, 2013) also show significant progress in the skill level of soccer athletes due to the impact of individual exercises.

(Birrer & Morgan, 2010) points out that one of the most prominent characteristics of sports training is that sports training is an educational process of a very individual nature, as it takes into consideration individual differences. The training process varies for each player according to his position in the team and the required physical and psychological skills and abilities.

(Dellal et al. 2008) noted that the analysis of the various tournaments and competition allows the coach to know the level of his players compared to the major teams, allowing him to direct his players through the principle of individual training according to the play position and according to the requirements of competition by engaging lengthening and flexibility exercises.

The researcher points to one of the important factors leading to a decrease in the efficiency of the technical performance of the players during the competition, which is the factor of duration and calendar championship professional, through the programming is not scientifically studied for the competitions and the passage of this tournament many interruptions during the sports season in addition to the length of the transitional period that may reach To more than three months free of effort, training and activity and thus retract the level of physical fitness leading to a lack and weakness in the effectiveness of the implementation of basic skills during competition.

In this regard, the results of the study (*Rampinini and coll, 2009:230*) indicate that the duration of competition may play an important role in influencing technical performance, so that the duration of competition, whether intensive, intensive or low, may negatively affect the skillful performance of soccer players. (Mujika, 2000) supports this proposition and believes that the discontinuation of training, whether it is a total or partial interruption, leads to a change in the physical and physiological adaptations of the body and a lack of athletic performance. It results in a gradual decline in the level of skill performance in the various activities. The quality and quantity of physiological and physical adaptations lost. The results of (Fleck,1994) confirms that the fallout from training in the changes in the body and muscle lead to a low level of performance as the athlete's ability to decrease by (10%) each week.

When analyzing the basic skills share of technical performance during competition, we found that there was a significant variance and superiority of offensive skill performance compared to defense skill performance (72% vs 28%). This means that players perform basic offensive skills such as dribbling and shooting the ball much higher than skills of tackling and hit the ball with head, and attributed to the researcher to the lack of participation and contribution of attackers and midfielders offensive in the defense in competition, since the attackers are considered the first line of defense of the team should be working to put pressure on the opponent And to discourage the building of the attack to the opponent team and this using the defensive basic skills such as tackling and hit the ball with the head and the cross and this will strike a balance between the performance of defensive and offensive skills.

Conclusion

Through our study, we analyzed the most important characteristics of the skill performance of professional soccer players in the first Algerian championship

To achieve the objectives of our study, we selected a sample of (72) professional soccer players. We also used the observation sheet to analyze and evaluate skill performance during competition.

The results of the study also showed that the percentage of participation of offensive skills in the overall performance during competition is much greater than the percentage of participation of defensive skills (72% versus 28%), and this proves that modern soccer has an offensive playing style, and that the players' mastery of skills using the

ball has a positive impact on the tactical aspect of the team (imposing the tactical system During the match, collective possession of the ball, keeping the ball, finishing attacks and scoring goals, etc.)

However, the results of the effectiveness of the performance of defensive and offensive skills were weak and did not reach the high level in most of the skill indicators studied.

Based on the results of this study, the researchers recommend:

- Giving great importance to skill training in the process of formation and preparing soccer players.
- Programming intensive skill training units in the planning for the sports season.
- Conduct similar studies on high-level European soccer players.

References

- Carling Christopher (2007), Handbook of Soccer Match Analysis, Edition Routledge, London, p1.
- Kellis E, Katis A. (2007) Biomechanical characteristics and determinants of instep soccer kick. *J Sports Sci Med* ; 6 : 154–165.
- Thomas Reily, (2007) The Science of Training – Soccer, Edition Routledge, London, p16.
- Ali Ajmol (April 2011), Measuring soccer skill performance: a review, *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine and Science in Sports* .
- Dôbler H (1988), Développement du soccer dans les jeux olympiques, Zikens.
- Eriksson S. G., Railo W. & Matson H., Sven Göran Eriksson (2001) on soccer- the inner game and improving performance, Eds Reedswain INC.
- Dellal A., Barriou P., Castagna C., Chamari K., Chouachi A., Chinelli S., Coutts A. J., Dyon N., Hagist L., Impellizzeri F., Moalla W., Monkam Tchokonte S. A., Pintus A., Rampinini E. & Reiss D (2008), De l'entraînement à la performance en soccer, Edition De Boeck, Bruxelles,.
- Di Salvo V., Barron R., Tschan H., Calderon Montero F., Bachl N. & Pigozzi F. (2007), Performance characteristics According to playing position in Elite Soccer INT, *J. Sports Med.*, 28(3): 222-227.
- MACKENZIE R. & CUSHION C. (2013), Performance analysis in soccer: A critical review and implications for future research, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, Vol. 31, No. 6, 639,2013.

- Martin Lee, the use of video feedback as a performance analysis coaching tool in amateur level ice hockey,
- Hughes, M & Franks, I. (2008 Editors) The Essentials of Performance Analysis. An Introduction. Routledge. Canada.
- Desmond Mcewan & Mark Beauchamp, (January 2014) Teamwork in sport: a theoretical and integrative review, International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology ·
- Ante Rađa and coll, (2019) The ball kicking speed: A new, efficient performance indicator in youth soccer, Daniel Boullosa, James Cook University College of Healthcare Sciences, BRAZIL.
- Serranojmrs J., Shahidian S., Sampaio J. & Leite N. (2013), The Importance of Sports Performance Factors and Training Contents From the Perspective of Futsal Coaches, Journal of Human Kinetics volume 38, 151-160.
- Birrer D. & Morgan .(2010) , Psychological skills training as a way to enhance an athlete's performance in high-intensity sports, IScand J Med Sci Sports: 20 (Suppl. 2): 78–87.
- Mujika I. (2000), Detraining: Loss of training induced part short term insufficient training stimulus, *sport Med journal*, 42-57.
- Rampinini E., Impellizzeri M F., Castagna C., J.Coutts A. J., & Wisløff U. (2009), Technical performance during soccer matches of the Italian Serie A league: Effect of fatigue and competitive level, *Journal of science and medicine in sport*, Volume 12, Issue 1, 227-233.
- Fleck S. J. (1994), Detraining, its effect on endurance strength, strength Cond. Sport science technology division U.S. Olympic Committee.